

Modelling of electrokinetic techniques for soil remediation and ground improvement. State of the art and assessment of research opportunities.

Rubén López-Vizcaíno*, Vicente Navarro, Ángel Yustres*

Geoenvironmental Group, Department of Civil Engineering and Construction, Civil Engineering School, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Camilo José Cela s/n, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain

Corresponding Authors* ruben.lopezvizcaino@uclm.es and angel.yustres@uclm.es; Geoenvironmental Group, Department of Civil Engineering and Construction, Civil Engineering School, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Camilo José Cela s/n, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a review of the state of the art concerning the simulation of electrokinetic techniques used in soil stabilisation and remediation processes. The main THMC models as well as those specifically designed for the simulation of electrokinetic phenomena have been presented. After evaluating the main characteristics of each of them, the need for a THMC model that also considers electrokinetic phenomena and their coupling with other physic-chemical processes has been identified.

KEYWORDS

Modelling; Simulation; Electrokinetic; Soils; THMC model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global growth of urbanised areas has been continuous over the last few years [1], being the only land use that has grown consistently across all continents. Between 1992 and 2018, 1.02 ± 0.78 million km² of urban land has been created. (This growth has mainly taken place in three ways. (1) The occupation of adjoining rural and agricultural land, much of it located in floodplains or deltas due to its high fertility, which can present (i) high deformability due to its recent alluvial nature and (ii) high levels of contamination by pesticides and/or fertilisers due to the intensive agriculture characteristic of these sites. (2) The occupation of former industrial land, in some cases contaminated due to human negligence. (3) Seaward expansion, where it is expected that unconsolidated sediments will be used for these expansion and infill works (globally available quality granular materials are scarce), with significant future seating problems as has already occurred in some relevant projects.

Soil remediation and land improvement are fields in which there will be increasing activity and, among other technologies, electrokinetic techniques will become increasingly important, especially because (i) they can be supported by renewable energy sources [2, 3] and their main cost can be greatly reduced and (ii) they favour the mobilisation of species and liquid phase by different mechanisms in media where hydraulic permeability is very low and hydraulic gradients are not effective in conventional soil washing [4].

However, the application of these techniques triggers a series of coupled processes that make the application of electrical gradients in soils an extremely complex phenomenon. The accelerated drainage of water from the soil pores due to electroosmosis leads to an increase in effective soil stresses and the rate of consolidation [5]. This implies changes in soil porosity and consequently in the effective diffusion coefficients of chemical species, soil deformability, hydraulic conductivity and electroosmotic permeability coefficients. The electromigratory phenomenon and electroosmotic advective transport alters the initial chemical equilibrium between soil and pore water. This leads to changes in the internal structure of the soil and to cementation of solid particles by dissolution and/or precipitation of minerals [6]. Moreover, the electrochemical reactions that occur on the surface of the electrodes (mainly water hydrolysis) can alter the entire geochemical system and therefore the mechanical behaviour of the soils. In addition, if the electric

current is high and the resistance of the soil is also high, the Joule effect can cause soil heating [7, 8].

In this context, a numerical model to understand all the coupled physic-chemical phenomena in soils during electrokinetic treatment is essential for the design, construction, and monitoring of these systems. Significant modelling efforts have been made for electro-hydro-mechanical problems, for electro-hydro-geochemical problems and for thermo-hydro-geochemical and mechanical problems that do not have external electric fields applied, but so far, no numerical model is available that is capable of reproducing all these phenomena in a coupled manner. This paper presents an updated review of the state of the art, thanks to which it has been possible to identify the main needs for progress in this area.

Firstly, the main models developed for the simulation of the Thermo-Hydro-Chemical-Mechanical behaviour of low permeability soils have been identified. Then, the main examples of modelling electrokinetic techniques in soil improvement and stabilisation processes as well as in decontamination treatment have been presented. Finally, the type of experimental results available to qualify the models developed have been checked and, as conclusions, the main research needs have been highlighted.

2. NUMERICAL THMC MODELS IN LOW PERMEABILITY SOILS

The modelling of the thermo-hydro-chemical-mechanical behaviour of low-permeability soils has developed mainly from the study and design of deep geological repositories for high-level radioactive waste. Thus, from the 1980s onwards, the first thermohydraulic models were developed (TH) [9], from the 1990s onwards the thermo-hydro-mechanical models (THM) [10-12] and in the new century the thermo-hydro-mechanical-chemical models (THMC) [13-19]. Research projects such as DECOVALEX [20] have been promoted with the aim of developing, validating and continuously improving codes that are able to solve coupled problems in clays. As a compilation, Table 1 presents the most used numerical codes currently shown. Although in most cases the codes are under continuous development, they are mainly oriented to the resolution of very specific bentonite problems, such as engineering barriers in radioactive waste disposal. None of them have considered including the resolution of electrokinetic phenomena.

Table 1. Main THMC models for clays

CODE NAME	INSTITUTION	REFERENCES
CODE_BRIGHT BExCM	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	[13, 14, 21]
FADES-CORE	Universidade de A Coruña	[10, 17, 22-27]
TOUGHREACT-FLAC	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	[18, 27-33]
COMPASS - PHREEQC	Cardiff University/ University of Manchester	[34-40]
AALTO-THEBES	Aalto University	[41-45]
UCLM - Model	Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha	[19, 46-52]
iCP (COMSOL – PHREEQC)	Amphos 21	[53, 54]

3. NUMERICAL MODELS OF ELECTROKINETIC SOIL IMPROVEMENT

Due to the development of soil stabilisation and drainage and sludge thickening, analytical solutions for coupled hydromechanical problems have been gradually developed, as they usually assume constant electric potential distributions over time and therefore do not depend on soil deformation, volumetric water content or salinity (Table 2). However, they are of great interest because they allow the verification of numerical models in a very efficient way. On the other hand, the increasing complexity of this type of solutions does not make them accessible to most of the scientific community and, in many cases, they are relegated to a mere mathematical exercise with hardly any practical application.

Table 2. Compilation of the main analytical and semi-analytical solutions to the HME problem

AUTHORS	YEAR	REF.	DESCRIPTION
Esrig	1968	[55]	First analytical solution available. 1D Solution
Wan, Mitchell	1976	[56]	Preload effects. 1D solution
Shang	1998	[57]	2D Solution
Shang	1998	[58]	2D Solution
Su, Wang	2003	[59]	2D Solution
Iwata, Jami	2010	[60]	1D solution including creeping
Wu, Hu	2013	[61]	2D axisymmetric solution
Wu, Qi, Hu, Wen	2017	[62]	1D semi-analytical solution. Non-linear variation of parameters
Zhao, Liu, Gong	2020	[63]	Two-layer 1D solution
Wang, Huang, Liu, Alonso	2020	[64]	Axisymmetric solution. Combination with vacuum pre-consolidation techniques
Wang, Shen, Liu, Alonso, Huang	2021	[65]	Unsaturated. Non-linear variation of parameters. 1D solution
Wang, Wang, Liu, Huang	2021	[66]	Unsaturated. Initial partial saturation not homogeneous. 1D solution
Liu, Zheng, Zhao, Cao, Huang	2021	[67]	Axisymmetric solution. Considers the effects of eddying.

In parallel to the analytical developments, numerical models of increasing complexity have also been developed (Table 3), going from one-dimensional to two- and three-dimensional models, in situations of partial saturation and with increasingly complex elastoplastic models. These models do resolve the electric field, although they do not at any time take into account the salinity of the interstitial water for their calculation or the degree of saturation.

Table 3. Compilation of the main numerical models of the HME problem

AUTHORS	YEAR	REF.	DESCRIPTION
Lewis, Garner	1972	[68]	2D solution. Finite elements.
Feldkamp, Belhomme	1990	[69]	Large deformations. 1D solution. Finite element.
Rittirong, Shang	2008	[70]	Variable deformability in time and space. Finite differences.
Yuan, Hicks, Dijkstra	2012	[71]	Multidimensional. Finite Elements
Hu, Wu, Wu	2012	[72]	Non-linear variation of hydraulic, mechanical and electroosmotic properties
Yuan, Hicks, Dijkstra	2013	[71]	Elastoplastic Cam-Clay model. Finite elements.
Yuan, Hicks	2013	[73]	Large deformations. 2D solution. Finite elements
Zhou, Deng, Wang	2013	[74]	Large deformations, soil self-weight and non-linear variation of soil properties. Finite differences.
Jeyakanthan, Gnanendran	2013	[75]	Elastoplasticity. Modified Cam Clay. Finite Elements.
Yuan, Hicks	2015	[76]	Large Deformations. Finite elements. Non-linear variations of parameters. Model elastoplastic model (modified Cam-Clay)
Deng, Zhou	2016	[77]	Large deformations. Preloading and electroconsolidation. 2D solution. Differences finite
Zhou, Deng	2019	[78]	Large deformations, soil self-weight and non-linear variation of soil properties. Finite differences. 3D axisymmetric
Zhou, Deng, Fu	2019	[79]	Unsaturated. Combination with preload. Large deformations. Non-linear changes of properties. Finite differences.
Wang, Liu, Wang, Xue	2019	[80]	Unsaturated. Non-linear changes of properties. Finite elements

4. NUMERICAL MODELS OF ELECTROKINETIC SOIL REMEDIATION

There is an extensive number of numerical models that have tackled the problem of soil remediation by means of electrokinetic techniques. In general, the major problem with this type of problem is the lack of flexibility due to the wide variety of contaminants and geochemical systems. Thus, most of the models are oriented towards solving very specific problems. In general, the treatment of soil as a porous medium is often poor, especially in clayey soils. There is no mechanical interaction and the role of temperature in the generation of heat by the Joule effect is not usually considered. Therefore, electro-hydro-

geochemical models can be considered. The models shown in Table 4 have been compiled from [81]. A review of the models developed in the last 10 years has recently been published, analysing in detail their main characteristics [82]. It has been observed that the development in recent years is increasingly accelerated, thanks to multiphysics codes such as COMSOL, which allow an implementation based on editing the coefficients of the partial, ordinary or algebraic differential equations of the model.

Table 4. Compilation of the main HCE numerical models of the electrokinetic remediation [81]

CODE NAME	AUTHORS	REF.
DIFFUSE	Acar, Alshawabkeh, Gale	[83]
MODFLOW-MT3D	Mattson, Bowman, Lindgren	[84, 85]
EKGEO-CHEM	Al-Hamdan, Reddy	[86]
M4EKR	Lopez-Vizcaino, Yustres, Leon, Saez, Cañizares, Rodrigo, Navarro	[87]
NP-Phreeqc-EK	Sprocati, Masi, Muniruzzaman, Rolle	[88]
SE-EK Model	Sun, Wu, Guo, Wang, Guo	[89]
SEKRET Model	Masi, Ceccarini, Iannelli	[90]

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AVAILABLE FOR MODEL QUALIFICATION

Experimental work on the study of electrokinetic processes in soils is extensive. In the case of soil remediation, growth has been exponential as shown in the literature review of Mao [91]. The work carried out in China, but also in Spain, is particularly noteworthy for its growth. The diversity of pollutants, modes of operation, combinations of treatments and possible improvements mean that the volume is now practically unmanageable.

As for electroconsolidation, although the production has also been very high, it has been mainly aimed at the validation of numerical models. Practically all the analytical solutions and models shown in Table 2 and Table 3 also show the experimental results used for validation. These are usually highly controlled tests, with well-defined initial and boundary conditions. Deng y Zhou [77] make a compilation of different experimental set-ups and the main results obtained.

In addition, much experimental work is being developed for the mechanical characterisation of soils subjected to electrical gradients [92-97] and to characterise the electromigration of ions in bentonites to be used in radioactive waste repositories [98-106]. The latter application is just beginning to be developed and may be of interest to accelerate experimental results on bentonites which, due to their low permeability, are very time-consuming, complex and costly. The results of these tests are promising, but

still require a numerical model to fully understand them and to be able to study the relative importance of the physicochemical phenomena involved. Since the electrical gradient is imposed only to accelerate the movement of water and solutes, if parameters unrelated to the electrokinetic processes are to be obtained, all the processes must be understood and modelled in a coupled way in order to correctly separate the contributions of each of them.

6. RESEARCH REQUIEREMENTS

As we have seen, both modelling and experimentation of electrokinetic techniques applied to soils have developed in two parallel areas: electroconsolidation and electrokinetic remediation, with two very different approaches. The first application has been developed in the field of civil engineering, while the second has been developed mainly within chemical engineering. This has generated a common and unifying approach to study the phenomenon in all its complexity. However, a more comprehensive study is required, with a numerical model to assess the impact of the coupling of all phenomena, and to improve the understanding of the large amount of experimental work done as well as the design of future tests.

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